

Research Article

A new combination in Indian *Calamus* (Arecaceae)

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Abstract: The species *Daemonorops teraiensis* Sujit Mondal & M.Chowdhury is herein transferred to the genus *Calamus* L., resulting in the new combination *Calamus teraiensis* (Sujit Mondal & M.Chowdhury) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar.

Keywords: *Daemonorops teraiensis*, Endemic, West Bengal

Introduction

The genus *Calamus* L. comprises about 418 species, distributed in tropical Africa, tropical and subtropical Asia to southwest Pacific. (Henderson 2020; POWO, 2025). In India, the genus is represented by 37 species, namely *C. acanthospathus* Griff., *C. andamanicus* Kurz, *C. baratangensis* Renuka & Vijayak., *C. brandisii* Becc., *C. dilaceratus* Becc., *C. erectus* Roxb., *C. flagellum* Griff. ex Walp., *C. floribundus* Griff., *C. gamblei* Becc., *C. gracilis* Roxb., *C. guruba* Buch.-Ham. ex Mart., *C. henryanus* Becc., *C. hookerianus* Becc., *C. karnatakensis* Renuka & Lakshmana, *C. inermis* T.Anderson, *C. kingianus* Becc., *C. lakshmanae* Renuka, *C. latifolius* Roxb., *C. leptospadix* Griff., *C. longisetus* Griff., *C. mahanandensis* S.Mondal, S.K.Basu & M.Chowdhury, *C. meghalayensis* A.J.Hend., *C. melanochaetes* (Blume) Miq., *C. metzianus* Schltld., *C. nagbettai* R.R.Fernandez & Dey, *C. nicobaricus* Becc., *C. pseudoerectus* Sujit Mondal, S.K.Basu & M.Chowdhury, *C. pseudotenuis* Becc., *C. rheedei* Griff., *C. rotang* L., *C. tenuis* Roxb., *C. teraiensis* (Sujit Mondal & M.Chowdhury), R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *C. thwaitesii* Becc. *C. unifarius* H.Wendl., *C. vattayila* Renuka, *C. viminalis* Willd. and *C. wightii* Griff. (Sreekumar & Henderson 2014; Henderson 2020; POWO, 2025). Among these, *C. andamanicus*, *C. baratangensis*, *C. brandisii*, *C. dilaceratus*, *C. gamblei*, *C. hookerianus*, *C. karnatakensis*, *C. lakshmanae*, *C. mahanandensis*, *C. meghalayensis*, *C. nagbettai*, *C. nicobaricus*, *C.*

pseudoerectus, *C. rheedei*, *C. teraiensis*, *C. vattayila* and *C. wightii* are endemic to India. The species *Daemonorops teraiensis* Sujit Mondal & M.Chowdhury is here transferred to the genus *Calamus*, following recent molecular phylogenetic studies that support the inclusion of *Daemonorops* Blume within *Calamus* (Baker et al., 2000; Baker, 2015). Accordingly, the new combination *Calamus teraiensis* (Sujit Mondal & M.Chowdhury) R.Kr. Singh & Sanjeet Kumar is proposed here.

New combination

Calamus teraiensis (Sujit Mondal & M.Chowdhury) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Daemonorops teraiensis* Sujit Mondal & M.Chowdhury, Pl. Arch. 19(Suppl. 2): 758. 2019.

Holotype: India, West Bengal. Darjeeling district, Dalkajhar forest at terai of Darjeeling (Jore Pokhri Wildlife Sanctuary), 26° 41' 42" N, 88° 17' 14" E, 145 m, 1 May 2018, S. Mondal & M. Chowdhury 0070 (CAL).

Distribution: Endemic to Darjeeling, West Bengal, India.

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